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Pancasila and the Law of the State: Ideals, Implementation, and Constitutional Reality in Indonesia

*Pancasila dan Hukum Negara: Cita-cita, Implementasi,
dan Realitas Konstitusional di Indonesia*

Febrianto Putra Pamungkas^{1✉}, Ahmad Zulfikar Abdur Razaak²

¹ Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia

² Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia

✉ Corresponding email: febrianto.pamungkas@unair.ac.id

Abstract

In a society, to guarantee togetherness in the life of the state, it is necessary to formulate a common goal or ideals which is called the state philosophy or state idea which functions as groundslag philosophy and common platform among fellow citizens in the context of constitutional life. The formulation of the state's philosophical basis or state ideology contained in the Preamble of the 1945 Constitution is Pancasila. The formulation of the Pancasila can also be referred to as the basic formula of the legal ideals of the Republic of Indonesia. As the ideals of the

state, of course it must be formulated based on the ideals that live in the society that existed before this country was founded. Legal development is all human activities with regard to the existence and enactment of law in society. Legal development includes theoretical and practical aspects. It should include principles in accordance with the values of Pancasila as the implementation of a pluralistic and national ideology civilization, to be a guideline for national and state law.

Keywords

Pancasila; Law; Ideology

Abstrak

Di suatu masyarakat, untuk menjamin kebersamaan dalam kehidupan bernegara, diperlukan perumusan dengan tujuan atau cita-cita bersama yang disebut sebagai falsafah kenegaraan atau staatsidee (cita negara) yang berfungsi sebagai filosofische grondslag dan common platform diantara sesama warga masyarakat dalam konteks kehidupan ketatanegaraan. Rumusan dasar filosofis negara atau ideologi negara yang terkandung oleh Pembukaan UUD 1945 adalah Pancasila. Rumusan Pancasila tersebut dapat pula disebut sebagai rumusan dasar dari cita hukum (rechtsidee) negara Republik Indonesia. Sebagai cita negara, tentunya ia harus dirumuskan berdasarkan cita yang hidup di dalam masyarakat yang telah ada sebelum negara ini didirikan. Pengembangan hukum adalah segala kegiatan manusia berkenaan dengan adanya dan berlakunya hukum dalam masyarakat. Pengembangan hukum meliputi aspek teoritis dan praktis. Perlu kiranya dimasukkan asas-asas yang sesuai dengan nilai-nilai Pancasila sebagai implementasi ideologi bangsa yang majemuk dan berkeadaban, untuk menjadi pedoman bagi hukumberbangsa

Kata Kunci

Pancasila; Hukum; Ideologi

A. Introduction

Pancasila, as the philosophical foundation of the Republic of Indonesia, was established through the consensus reached during the sessions of the Investigating Committee for Preparatory Work for Indonesian Independence (BPUPKI).¹ The term *Pancasila*, which literally means "five principles," had been known since the Majapahit era and is mentioned in the *Sutasoma* by Mpu Tantular and the *Nagarakretagama* by Mpu Prapanca.² On 18 August 1945, Pancasila was officially adopted as the foundation of the Indonesian state.³ Since then, the values guiding the life of the nation and the administration of the state have been based on Pancasila. As a national consensus, Pancasila is accepted by all ideologies, groups, and segments of Indonesian society.⁴

In the context of constitutional law, Pancasila is closely associated with its status as the foundation of the state. As the state's philosophical foundation, Pancasila serves as the basis for regulating national governance, meaning that all laws and regulations as well as policies enacted by state authorities must not contradict the values embodied in Pancasila.⁵ The principles of Pancasila are elaborated in the provisions of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. Therefore, discussing Pancasila within the framework of constitutional law essentially

¹ Naskah Komprehensif Perubahan Undang-Undang Dasar Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun 1945, *Naskah Komprehensif Perubahan Undang-Undang Dasar Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun 1945: Latar Belakang, Proses, dan Hasil Pembahasan, Buku I: Latar Belakang, Proses, dan Hasil Pembahasan 1945-1959* (Jakarta: Sekretariat Jenderal dan Kepaniteraan Mahkamah Konstitusi Republik Indonesia, 2010), 71-89.

² *Sutasoma*, trans. Soewito Santoso (New Delhi: International Academy of Indian Culture and Aditya Prakashan, 1975), 578-579; *Nagarakretagama*, trans. Theodore G. Th. Pigeaud, *Java in the Fourteenth Century*, vol. 3 (The Hague: Martinus Nijhoff, 1962).

³ Undang-Undang Dasar Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun 1945, Preamble, adopted on 18 August 1945.

⁴ Kaelan, *Pendidikan Pancasila* (Yogyakarta: Paradigma, 2016), 45-56.

⁵ Notonagoro, *Pancasila: Dasar Falsafah Negara* (Jakarta: Bina Aksara, 1988), 83-95.

means discussing the constitutional provisions contained in the articles of the 1945 Constitution. Article 1 paragraph (1) of the amended 1945 Constitution affirms that Indonesia is a unitary state in the form of a republic.

Tracing the deliberations of the BPUPKI and PPKI sessions demonstrates that, from the very beginning of its formulation, Pancasila was intended to serve as the *philosophische grondslag* (philosophical foundation) of the state, or the philosophical basis of the Republic of Indonesia. Accordingly, the Indonesian state was conceived and established upon the philosophical values embodied in Pancasila. As a logical consequence, the Indonesian state and its constitutional system must place Pancasila as their spiritual and philosophical foundation, meaning that the spirit, values, and principles of Pancasila should permeate and inspire every aspect of the state and its governance. This position is explicitly affirmed in Article 2 of Law Number 12 of 2011 on the Formulation of Laws and Regulations, which stipulates that Pancasila constitutes the source of all sources of state law.

In the *Sutasoma*, the term *Pancasila* refers to the “five principles of moral conduct” (*Pancasila Krama*), namely: refraining from violence, refraining from theft, refraining from envy, refraining from falsehood, and refraining from consuming intoxicating beverages. The state, through its various functions and objectives, seeks to realize these ideals by employing different mechanisms. As the institutional integration of political power, the state possesses several inherent characteristics, including the authority to compel obedience, the monopoly over the legitimate use of force, and the capacity to regulate all aspects of public life. Through its coercive authority, the state may legitimately employ physical force to ensure compliance with its laws and decisions.

In general, ideology may be classified into open and closed ideologies. According to Franz Magnis-Suseno, a closed ideology is a doctrine, worldview, or philosophical system that prescribes political and social objectives and norms as absolute truths that are beyond question and therefore must be accepted and obeyed without criticism.

Following Indonesia's independence, the national legal order gradually regained the characteristics of customary law (*adat law*) as part of strengthening the nation's identity and demonstrating the sovereignty of the newly independent state. Consequently, constitutional thought and legal development increasingly reflected indigenous Indonesian values rather than colonial legal traditions. During this period, legal development sought to realize the legal ideals (*rechtsidee*) existing within Indonesian society, with legal practice functioning as an instrument to reinforce national identity and nationalism. Nevertheless, the administration of the state continued to rely, to a considerable extent, on legal provisions inherited from the Dutch colonial administration.

In Indonesia, the ideology of Pancasila represents the manifestation of the social, cultural, and historical conditions that united the Indonesian people in their determination to establish an independent state. To realize this aspiration, Pancasila was adopted as the philosophical foundation of the state, with its five principles embodying the fundamental values of the Indonesian nation. As both the foundation of the state and the national way of life, Pancasila has possessed constitutional legitimacy since 18 August 1945, the date on which the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia was formally adopted.

B. Method

This study employs a normative legal research approach, also referred to as doctrinal legal research, to examine the constitutional position of Pancasila as the philosophical foundation of the Indonesian state and the source of all sources of law. The research is based on a conceptual, statutory, and historical approach. The conceptual approach is used to analyze the philosophical and theoretical foundations of Pancasila as the state's ideology and constitutional norm. The statutory approach examines the relevant constitutional and legislative framework, particularly the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia and Law Number 12 of 2011 on the Formulation of Laws and Regulations, as amended by Law Number 13 of 2022. The historical approach is employed to trace the formulation of Pancasila through the deliberations of the Investigating

Committee for Preparatory Work for Indonesian Independence (BPUPKI) and the Preparatory Committee for Indonesian Independence (PPKI), thereby providing historical context for its constitutional status.

The legal materials consist of primary, secondary, and tertiary sources. Primary legal materials include the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, statutory regulations, official constitutional documents, and records of the BPUPKI and PPKI proceedings. Secondary legal materials comprise scholarly books, peer-reviewed journal articles, legal commentaries, and academic publications concerning constitutional law, legal philosophy, Pancasila, and Indonesian legal development. Tertiary legal materials, including legal dictionaries and encyclopedias, are used to support conceptual clarification.

C. Result and Discussion

1. Pancasila as the Foundational Principle of the Indonesian Legal System

In every society, the preservation of collective life within the state requires the formulation of shared objectives and ideals, commonly referred to as the philosophy of the state (*staatsidee* or the ideal of the state). This philosophy functions as the *philosophische grondslag* (philosophical foundation) and as a *common platform* that unites citizens within the framework of constitutional governance.⁶ Pancasila serves as Indonesia's philosophy of the state and its national ideal because it constitutes the constitutional foundation of the Indonesian legal order. Its philosophical status is explicitly embodied in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, which represents the original constitutional consensus upon which Indonesian constitutionalism is founded.

The concept of Pancasila as the *staatsfundamentalnorn* was first articulated by Notonagoro, who regarded Pancasila as the state's fundamental norm and as the nation's legal ideal

⁶ Jimly Asshiddiqie, *Konstitusi dan Konstitusionalisme Indonesia*, 2nd ed. (Jakarta: Sinar Grafika, 2006), 25–34.

(*rechtsidee*).⁷ Consequently, once Pancasila was established as the *staatsfundamentalnorm*, every stage of legal development including law-making, interpretation, implementation, and enforcement must remain consistent with the values and principles embodied in Pancasila.⁸

In the process of law-making, the state inevitably pursues certain legal objectives. According to the utilitarian theory advanced by Jeremy Bentham, the primary purpose of law is to maximize utility or the greatest happiness for the greatest number of people. By contrast, legal positivist and legalistic theories emphasize that the principal objective of law is to ensure legal certainty, whereby legal rules provide predictability, consistency, and stability in the administration of justice. One of the most significant roles of Pancasila since the establishment of the Republic of Indonesia has been its function in unifying the Indonesian people and shaping Indonesia as a nation with a distinct identity and confidence in its own values. From the outset of statehood, Indonesian society has been characterized by extraordinary diversity.

It is a multiethnic, multireligious, and ideologically pluralistic society. Such diversity creates dynamic interactions among its various elements. On the one hand, these differences constitute valuable cultural resources that enrich the nation and strengthen national development. On the other hand, they also have the potential to generate social conflict, disputes, and divisions that may undermine national unity. Given these circumstances, the foremost challenge faced by the newly independent Indonesian state was to establish national unity and consolidate the collective strength required for effective state-building. Within this political context, Pancasila has been conceived as an ideology of national unity, providing a common philosophical foundation capable of accommodating Indonesia's social, cultural, religious, and political diversity.

The philosophical foundation of the Indonesian state, as embodied in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution, is

⁷ Notonagoro, *Pancasila: Dasar Falsafah Negara* (Jakarta: Bina Aksara, 1988), 95–110.

⁸ Maria Farida Indrati, *Ilmu Perundang-undangan: Jenis, Fungsi, dan Materi Muatan*, rev. ed. (Yogyakarta: Kanisius, 2007), 44–52.

Pancasila. The formulation of Pancasila also represents the legal ideal (*rechtsidee*) of the Republic of Indonesia. As the state's fundamental ideal, Pancasila derives its legitimacy from the values, aspirations, and collective consciousness that had long existed within Indonesian society (*Volksgemeinschaftsidee*) before the establishment of the state itself. This understanding is closely related to Hans Kelsen's theory of the hierarchy of norms (*Stufenbau Theory*), which maintains that the validity of every legal norm depends upon its creation in accordance with a higher legal norm. Accordingly, the hierarchical structure of legal norms reflects a relationship in which a superior norm provides the legal basis for the validity of subordinate norms. The relationship between norms governing the creation of other norms is therefore characterized by superordination and subordination: a norm authorizing the creation of another norm occupies a superior position, while the norm established pursuant to that authority is regarded as inferior. Within the Indonesian legal system, Pancasila occupies the highest normative position as the *staatsfundamentalnorm*, from which the Constitution and all subsequent legislation derive their legitimacy and normative authority.

In this context, the substantive content of every legislative enactment must reflect not only the hierarchical validity of legal norms as proposed by Hans Kelsen but also philosophical, sociological, and political considerations, all of which play a fundamental and strategic role in the legislative process. As a modern constitutional state (*Rechtsstaat*) founded upon the 1945 Constitution, Indonesia consciously seeks to achieve its constitutional objectives through legal and institutional development. Accordingly, social transformation is pursued through national development policies, legislative planning, and the enactment of laws and public policies designed to facilitate the implementation of the state's constitutional aspirations. Within the legislative process, Pancasila should therefore be positioned as the material source of law (*materiële rechtsbron*) underlying the formulation of statutory regulations. This position is expressly affirmed by Article 2 of Law Number 12 of

2011 on the Formulation of Laws and Regulations, which provides that "*Pancasila is the source of all sources of state law*".⁹

The recognition of Pancasila as the supreme source of law is consistent with the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution, in which Pancasila is established as the philosophical foundation and ideological basis of the Indonesian state. Consequently, every legislative enactment must be consistent with and give effect to the fundamental values embodied in Pancasila. In principle, there are two principal perspectives regarding the significance of legislative drafting. The first regards legislation primarily as an instrument for establishing legal certainty by providing clear, predictable, and enforceable legal norms. The second perceives legislation as a means of social engineering, through which the state directs social change and promotes justice, public welfare, and national development in accordance with constitutional values.¹⁰

According to T. Koopmans, legislation serves two principal functions. First, it codifies the norms and values that have become firmly embedded within society. Second, it functions as an instrument for modifying social life.¹¹ In a similar vein, I. C. van der Vlies argues that regulatory modification aims to transform the existing legal order and reshape prevailing social relationships through legislative intervention. Legislation is therefore essentially an interpretation of the collective will of society. This perspective is consistent with Eugen Ehrlich's concept of *living law*, which maintains that the law derives its legitimacy from the norms and practices actually observed within society, as well as with Friedrich Carl von Savigny's theory of *Volksgeist*, according to which law reflects the spirit and legal consciousness of the people.

Furthermore, Soerjono Soekanto emphasizes that one of the principal factors influencing the effectiveness of law enforcement is society itself. Consequently, a comprehensive

⁹ Undang-Undang Nomor 12 Tahun 2011 tentang Pembentukan Peraturan Perundang-undangan, art. 2.

¹⁰ Roscoe Pound, *Social Control through Law* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1942), 65–81; Jeremy Bentham, *An Introduction to the Principles of Morals and Legislation* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1907 [1789]), 1–18.

¹¹ T. Koopmans, *De Rol van de Wetgever* (Zwolle: W. E. J. Tjeenk Willink, 1970), 18–261.

sociological assessment of contemporary social conditions is indispensable in the drafting of every legislative proposal. Such an assessment ensures that legislation reflects social realities and can be effectively implemented, thereby contributing to good governance and the effective functioning of the state.

These principles are reinforced by Article 6 of Law Number 12 of 2011 on the Formulation of Laws and Regulations, which provides that the substantive content of legislation must embody the principles of protection, humanity, nationality, kinship, archipelagic unity, *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in Diversity), justice, equality before the law and government, legal order and certainty, as well as balance, harmony, and proportionality. Collectively, these legislative principles reflect the normative values embodied in the five principles of Pancasila. This raises an important question: to what extent do legislative drafters genuinely incorporate these constitutional principles throughout the legislative drafting process?

The legal principles outlined above serve to interpret legal rules and provide normative guidance for human conduct, although not as directly as specific rules of behavior. Legal principles explain and justify legal norms by embodying the ideological values that underpin the legal order. Consequently, legal norms derive not only their formal validity but also their substantive legitimacy from the fundamental principles upon which the legal system is constructed.¹² The norms and values embodied in Pancasila should therefore be translated into the substantive provisions of every legislative enactment so that statutory law reflects the values genuinely living within Indonesian society. Indeed, Indonesia's Founding Fathers derived the principles of Pancasila through a long process of observing and formulating the moral, cultural, and social values that had developed within Indonesian communities.

Consequently, legislation founded upon Pancasila is more likely to gain broad public acceptance because its underlying values originate from, and continue to evolve within, Indonesian

¹² Mohammad Hatta, *Pengertian Pancasila* (Jakarta: Idayu Press, 1977), 15–23; Yudi Latif, *Negara Pariwisata: Historisitas, Rasionalitas, dan Aktualitas Pancasila* (Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2011), 25–48.

society itself. The philosophy or worldview of a nation fundamentally consists of its moral and ethical values. These values distinguish what is considered good from what is considered undesirable and embody the ideals that a nation upholds. They include the values of truth, justice, morality, humanity, and other ethical principles regarded as essential to the life of the nation. As Indonesia's philosophical foundation, Pancasila embodies these moral values and provides the normative orientation for the development of the national legal system.

Accordingly, efforts to internalize the values of Pancasila within the legislative process should begin at the earliest stage of drafting legislation, namely through the preparation of the Academic Paper (*Naskah Akademik*).¹³ Indonesian legislative drafting procedures require every Academic Paper to provide both philosophical and sociological justifications for the proposed legislation. Therefore, the philosophical and sociological analyses contained in the Academic Paper should explicitly elaborate the values of Pancasila as the normative basis for legislative policy. Such an approach ensures that legislation is not merely formally valid but also substantively reflects the constitutional identity, moral aspirations, and living values of Indonesian society.

2. The Position of Pancasila in Indonesia's Legal Politics

Determining the position of Pancasila within Indonesia's legal politics is not a straightforward task. Different scholars have reached different conclusions depending on their theoretical perspectives and methodological approaches. This study approaches the issue from the perspective of constitutional law and legal philosophy, examining Pancasila as the normative foundation underlying Indonesia's legal and political system.

Since Indonesia's independence, Pancasila has consistently occupied a central position as the philosophical foundation of

¹³ Undang-Undang Nomor 12 Tahun 2011 tentang Pembentukan Peraturan Perundang-undangan, arts. 43-45 and the Appendix concerning the preparation of Academic Papers (*Naskah Akademik*).

the state, the national ideology, the nation's way of life, and the fundamental source of constitutional values. The five principles of Pancasila, as incorporated into the fourth paragraph of the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, continue to constitute the constitutional identity of the Indonesian state despite several constitutional amendments.

Historically, Pancasila was formally introduced by Sukarno on 1 June 1945 during the session of the Investigating Committee for Preparatory Work for Indonesian Independence (BPUPKI). It was conceived as the *philosophische grondslag* (philosophical foundation) and *rechtsidee* (legal ideal) of the future Indonesian state. Although the concept evolved through subsequent deliberations of the BPUPKI and the Preparatory Committee for Indonesian Independence (PPKI), its essential function as the philosophical basis of the Republic remained unchanged. From the perspective of constitutional theory, Pancasila constitutes the *staatsfundamentalnorn* of the Indonesian legal order, providing the highest normative foundation from which the Constitution and all legislation derive their legitimacy.

Beyond its constitutional status, Pancasila also embodies the ethical and philosophical values of Indonesian society. Rather than representing a purely political doctrine, it emerged from the historical, cultural, and social values that had long existed within Indonesian communities. Consequently, Pancasila functions simultaneously as the state's philosophical foundation, a unifying national ideology, and the normative framework guiding public policy and legal development. Within Indonesia's constitutional system, the values of Pancasila are not merely symbolic but are concretely reflected in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution. The principles of belief in God, humanity, national unity, democracy, and social justice are translated into constitutional objectives, including the protection of all Indonesians, the promotion of public welfare, the advancement of education, and participation in establishing a world order based on freedom, lasting peace, and social justice.

From the perspective of legal politics, Pancasila functions as the normative compass directing national legal development.

Legal politics itself constitutes a branch of legal science concerned with determining the direction, objectives, and policies of legal development. In this respect, Pancasila serves as the principal normative benchmark for legislative policy, law enforcement, and legal reform. Every legal policy should therefore reflect the philosophical values embodied in Pancasila while simultaneously responding to contemporary social, political, and economic developments.¹⁴

The relationship between law and politics is inherently reciprocal. Politics determines the direction of legal development, while law establishes the normative limits within which political power must operate. In the Indonesian context, this relationship should be understood within the framework of the constitutional state (*Rechtsstaat*), where political authority is exercised under the supremacy of law and guided by the values of Pancasila. Consequently, legal politics should strengthen constitutional democracy rather than facilitate authoritarian governance. Democratic political configurations provide opportunities for public participation, accountability, and representative decision-making, all of which are consistent with the fourth principle of Pancasila concerning democracy guided by wisdom through deliberation and representation.

Accordingly, Indonesia's national legal politics should continuously pursue the development of a legal system that reflects Pancasila while remaining responsive to societal transformation, globalization, and developments in international law. In this sense, Pancasila does not merely function as a historical symbol but remains a living constitutional norm that directs the formulation, implementation, and continuous renewal of Indonesia's legal system.¹⁵

¹⁴ Mahfud MD, *Politik Hukum di Indonesia*, rev. ed. (Jakarta: Rajawali Pers, 2017), 1–35.

¹⁵ Satjipto Rahardjo, *Hukum Progresif: Sebuah Sintesa Hukum Indonesia* (Yogyakarta: Genta Publishing, 2009), 45–62.

3. The Implementation of Pancasila Values in Laws and Regulations

The fourth paragraph of the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia explicitly embodies the five principles of Pancasila, which are subsequently elaborated in the constitutional provisions contained in the body of the Constitution. Accordingly, every constitutional provision must be interpreted as reflecting the philosophical values and constitutional spirit expressed in the Preamble. The philosophical foundation and state ideology embodied in the Preamble is Pancasila, which also constitutes the legal ideal (*rechtsidee*) of the Republic of Indonesia. As the state's legal ideal, Pancasila derives its legitimacy from the collective aspirations and values (*Volksgemeinschaftsidee*) that had long existed within Indonesian society prior to the establishment of the Republic.

As a legal ideal, Pancasila performs both constitutive and regulative functions. Its constitutive function provides the fundamental basis upon which the Indonesian legal order derives its legitimacy; without such a foundation, the legal system would lose its normative coherence and identity. At the same time, its regulative function serves as the normative standard for evaluating whether positive law reflects the principles of justice. Consequently, the values embodied in Pancasila determine not only the legitimacy of Indonesia's legal order but also whether statutory law can be regarded as substantively just.

This understanding is closely aligned with Hans Kelsen's theory of the hierarchy of norms (*Stufenbau Theory*), which maintains that the validity of every legal norm depends upon its conformity with a higher legal norm. Accordingly, the hierarchical structure of legal norms establishes a relationship in which superior norms provide the legal basis for the validity of subordinate norms. The relationship between norms governing the creation of other norms is therefore one of superordination and subordination: a norm authorizing the creation of another norm occupies a superior position, while the norm established pursuant to that authority occupies an inferior position. Within the Indonesian legal system, Pancasila

occupies the highest normative position as the *staatsfundamentalnorm*, from which the Constitution, legislation, and all subordinate legal instruments derive their legal validity. Consequently, the incorporation of Pancasila values into legislation is not merely a political or moral aspiration but a constitutional imperative that guarantees the coherence, legitimacy, and justice of the Indonesian legal system.

In this context, the substantive content of every legislative enactment must be informed not only by the hierarchical validity of legal norms, as proposed by Hans Kelsen, but also by philosophical, sociological, and political considerations. These dimensions are indispensable for ensuring that legislation possesses both formal validity and substantive legitimacy. As a modern constitutional state (*Rechtsstaat*) founded upon the 1945 Constitution, Indonesia consciously pursues its constitutional objectives through legal development and institutional reform. Consequently, social transformation is achieved through national development policies, legislative planning, statutory regulation, and public policies designed to implement the constitutional aspirations of the state.

¹⁶Within the legislative process, Pancasila should therefore be positioned as the material source of law (*materiële rechtsbron*) underlying the formulation of legislation. This constitutional status is explicitly affirmed in Article 2 of Law Number 12 of 2011 on the Formulation of Laws and Regulations, which provides that "Pancasila is the source of all sources of state law."² The recognition of Pancasila as the supreme source of law is fully consistent with the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution, which establishes Pancasila as the philosophical foundation and ideological basis of the Indonesian state. Consequently, every legislative enactment must be consistent with the fundamental values embodied in Pancasila.

Legislation should also be understood as an expression of the collective will of society. This view is consistent with Eugen Ehrlich's theory of *living law*, which recognizes that law derives its legitimacy from the norms and practices actually observed

¹⁶ Yudi Latif, *Negara Paripurna: Historisitas, Rasionalitas, dan Aktualitas Pancasila* (Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2011), 25–74.

within society, as well as Friedrich Carl von Savigny's concept of *Volksgeist*, according to which law reflects the spirit and legal consciousness of the people. Likewise, Soerjono Soekanto emphasizes that society itself constitutes one of the principal factors influencing the effectiveness of law enforcement. Therefore, comprehensive sociological analysis of contemporary social conditions is essential in the preparation of every legislative proposal.¹⁷ Legislation that genuinely reflects social realities is more likely to be accepted, effectively implemented, and capable of achieving its intended regulatory objectives. "This constitutional approach is further reinforced by Article 6 of Law Number 12 of 2011, which requires that the substantive content of legislation embody the principles of protection, humanity, nationality, kinship, archipelagic unity, *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in Diversity), justice, equality before the law and government, legal order and certainty, as well as balance, harmony, and proportionality.

Collectively, these legislative principles represent the constitutional values embodied in the five principles of Pancasila. Accordingly, an important question arises: to what extent do legislative drafters genuinely integrate these constitutional principles throughout the legislative drafting process? The answer to this question ultimately determines whether legislation merely satisfies formal procedural requirements or truly embodies the constitutional identity and philosophical values of the Indonesian legal system. A further question concerns the extent to which the values of Pancasila have been effectively incorporated into the drafting of legislation at both the national and regional levels. Although Indonesian legislation formally recognizes Pancasila as the source of all sources of state law, the large number of constitutional review cases before the Constitutional Court and judicial review proceedings before the Supreme Court suggests that legislative products do not always fully reflect the constitutional values embodied in Pancasila. This indicates that

¹⁷ Eugen Ehrlich, *Fundamental Principles of the Sociology of Law*, trans. Walter L. Moll (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1936), 390–398; Roscoe Pound, *Social Control through Law* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1942), 65–81.

legislative drafters have not consistently employed Pancasila as the primary normative foundation in the law-making process.¹⁸

The norms and values embodied in Pancasila should therefore be translated into substantive legislative provisions so that statutory law genuinely reflects the values, aspirations, and legal consciousness of Indonesian society. The Founding Fathers formulated Pancasila through a long process of identifying and synthesizing the moral, cultural, and social values that had long existed within Indonesian communities. Consequently, legislation grounded in Pancasila is more likely to gain public legitimacy and acceptance because it embodies values that continue to live, develop, and evolve within society itself. Accordingly, the development of Indonesia's legal system should consistently pursue the constitutional ideal envisioned by the founders of the Republic.

This constitutional vision should neither imitate the liberal-individualist tradition that historically accompanied colonialism and imperialism nor adopt the model of extreme collectivism associated with socialist-communist states. Instead, Indonesia's legal development should reflect the synthesis envisioned by the Founding Fathers, a distinct constitutional philosophy founded upon the values of Pancasila. Such an approach would enable legislation to achieve both philosophical and sociological legitimacy. Philosophically, legislation should embody the value system of Pancasila and serve as an instrument for realizing those values in social life. Sociologically, legislation should correspond to the realities, needs, and legal consciousness of society.

Consequently, an important issue remains whether legislative drafters have genuinely incorporated these constitutional principles throughout every stage of the legislative drafting process. Legal principles perform an essential interpretative function within the legal system. Although they do not regulate conduct as directly as specific legal rules, they provide normative guidance for interpreting legislation and justify the legal norms established by statutory

¹⁸ Mahkamah Konstitusi Republik Indonesia, *Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia* and constitutional review jurisprudence; Mahkamah Agung Republik Indonesia, judicial review jurisprudence under statutory law.

law. These principles embody the ideological values that sustain the legal order and ensure that legislation remains consistent with the constitutional identity of the Indonesian state.

D. Conclusion

To ensure unity and cohesion within a constitutional state, a nation requires a shared philosophical foundation or *staatsidee* (constitutional ideal) that functions as both the *philosophische grondslag* (philosophical foundation) and a common platform for public life. From the inception of the Republic, one of Pancasila's most significant functions has been its capacity to unify Indonesia's highly diverse society while shaping the nation's constitutional identity and fostering collective self-confidence. Accordingly, the implementation of Pancasila in public life is indispensable, particularly in the development of Indonesia's legal system. As the national ideology, Pancasila provides the normative foundation for the exercise of state authority and serves as the guiding legal ideal (*rechtsidee*) upon which legislation and public policy should be based.

The principal challenge, however, lies in ensuring that Pancasila functions not merely as an abstract legal ideal or constitutional aspiration but as a living normative framework that genuinely guides legislative drafting, legal interpretation, and law enforcement. As Indonesia's legal ideal, Pancasila performs both constitutive and regulative functions. Its constitutive function establishes the legitimacy and identity of the Indonesian legal order, whereas its regulative function provides the normative standard for assessing whether positive law embodies the principles of justice and constitutional values.

E. Competing Interest

None

F. References

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